

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B426
Date: 28 Jan 2009
Take Off: 08:42:05
Landing: 14:07:37
Flight Time: 5h 25m 32s

Campaign: APPRAISE
Operating Area: Chilbolton

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Luc Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	Manchester University	
5	Mission Scientist 2	Martin Gallagher	Manchester University	
6	Flight Manager / Core Chem / WAS	Alan Woolley	FAAM	
7	AMS	Jonny Crosier	Manchester University	
8	Manchester Cloud	Chris Dearden	Manchester University	
9	CVI	Jeff Norwood Brown	Met Office	
10	Cloud Physics	Kate Turnbull	Manchester University	
11	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	Simon Osborne	Met Office	
12	Mission Scientist 3	Zhiqiang Cui	Leeds University	
13				
14				
15				
16				
17				
18				

The following log sheets are not available for this flight :

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Xchat	No log available
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	No In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log available
Filters	No log as no filters exposed
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
Wet Neph	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
CVI	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created
WAS	Operator does not create a log sheet
Manchester Cloud	Manchester Cloud operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	30 Dec 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_090841_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_100841_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_110841_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_120841_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_130841_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_091042_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_101042_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_111042_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_121042_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_131042_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_091045_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_101045_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_111045_1hz.avi
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 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_111039_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_121039_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090128_r0_b426_131039_1hz.avi

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B426

Date: 28 January 2009

Project: Appraise

Location: Chilbolton

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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083158		Start-Up	0.36 kft	306	
083409		taxy	0.36 kft	306	
084205		T/O	0.37 kft	211	
090114	090820	Profile 1	8.5 - 2.6 kft	168	
090820		run 1.1	2.6 kft	171	
091409		run 1.1	2.6 kft	248	end
091409	093921	Profile 2	2.6 - 25.0 kft	249	
091631		Profile 2	4.0 kft	251	interrupt
091742		Profile 2	4.0 kft	250	resume
091907		jw/nevz zero	5.2 kft	210	
092120		cpc logging	7.1 kft	260	started
093928	094208	Run 2.1	25.1 - 25.0 kft	076	
094031		ovhd	25.0 kft	071	chil
094611	095212	Profile 3	25.0 - 19.0 kft	246	
095212	095528	Run 3.1	19.0 kft	255	
100442	100759	Run 3.2	19.0 kft	075	at 100000
100628		ovhd	19.0 kft	075	chilb
101234	102651	Profile 4	19.0 - 6.0 kft	254	
102652	102755	Run 4.1	6.0 kft	070	
102936	103719	Run 4.2	5.0 kft	071	
103543		ovhd	5.0 kft	071	chilb
104116	104430	Profile 5	5.1 - 2.6 kft	248	
104430	110156	Profile 6	2.6 - 20.0 kft	255	
110156	110900	Run 5.1	20.0 kft	072	
111321	111429	Profile 7	20.0 - 21.0 kft	253	
111429	112541	Run 6.1	21.0 kft	255	
112541	112647	Profile 8	21.0 - 20.0 kft	120	
112647	113712	Run 7.1	20.0 kft	088	
114122	114233	Profile 9	20.0 - 19.0 kft	250	
114233	115227	Run 8.1	19.0 kft	256	
115314	115532	Profile 10	19.0 - 17.1 kft	035	
115533	120630	Run 9.1	17.1 - 17.0 kft	078	
121026	121242	Profile 11	17.0 - 15.0 kft	248	
121242	122251	Run 10.1	15.0 kft	256	
122304	122509	Profile 12	15.0 - 13.0 kft	358	
122509	124242	Run 11.1	13.0 kft	098	
123552		ovhd	13.0 kft	068	chilb
124243	124359	Profile 13	13.0 - 14.0 kft	256	
124359	124912	Run 12.1	14.0 - 14.2 kft	259	
124912	125112	Profile 14	14.2 - 16.0 kft	255	
125113	130544	Run 13.1	16.0 kft	041	
125938		ovhd	16.0 kft	072	chilb
130544	130744	Profile 15	16.0 - 18.0 kft	236	
130744	131320	Run 14.1	18.0 kft	256	
131320	131539	Profile 16	18.0 - 20.0 kft	261	
131540	132741	Run 15.1	20.0 kft	117	
132226		ovhd	20.0 kft	075	chilb
132742	132857	Profile 17	20.0 - 19.0 kft	249	
132857	133438	Run 16.1	19.0 kft	258	
133438	133645	Profile 18	19.0 - 17.0 kft	254	
133645	134428	Run 17.1	17.0 kft	106	
134406		ovhd	17.0 kft	077	chilb
140737		Land	0.34 kft	209	Cranfield

Sortie Brief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies

**Date: 28 Jan 2009 – possible double flight B426a and b, or one full flight B426
B426(a) - Cranfield T/O 09:00z (if double flight land Cranfield ~13:00 to refuel)
B426b - Cranfield (if going ahead) T/O ~14:00z**

M.Sci: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Sortie Location: Over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. Area Alpha.

Sortie Summary: Perform a series of runs at a series of altitudes below cloud base (if possible), within and above the cloud, along the azimuth that is being scanned by the radar. Information on the run orientation and altitude to be flown will be provided by scientists at Chilbolton using VHF radio (call-sign “Radsearch”). Where the radar identifies a small-scale feature of interest, the aircraft may abort a long leg in order to turn to re-penetrate it. Where either the aircraft or radar identifies a particular horizontal layer of interest, the aircraft may fly a sawtooth pattern so as to provide a sequence of profiles through it. It is desired that the aircraft flight legs start/finish in the Chilbolton overhead. This benefits the validation of vertically-pointing radar/lidar retrievals of supercooled cloud layers. This requires turns to be done within controlled airspace and so may limit the number of occasions that this is possible.

Sortie Detail B426(a) :

- a) T+0 Take off & climb to FL100 to transit to operating area at Chilbolton.
- b) T+35 When at suitable location descend from transit altitude to 1000ft agl, or to lowest altitude allowed by operating restrictions (This may only be achieved with an approach to Boscombe Down airfield - TBD). Fly 10min **clear air** leg.
- c) Perform a profile ascent at 1000ft/min along the azimuth and through the cloud system up to FL330 or to above mid level cloud top, whichever is lower.
- d) Fly a series of 40-60km level flight legs along the azimuth scanned by the radar at altitudes defined by the radar or as determined from previous profile. Ideally, just above cloud base, throughout the cloud, just below and just above cloud top. Duration of each leg ~10 minutes. Legs should extend over Chilbolton. During incloud legs AMS should sample off CVI inlet unless tip iced up (but sample off Rosemount inlet out of cloud). Filters to be exposed on out of cloud legs only.
- e) Where the radar identifies a feature of interest or one that is penetrated by the aircraft along any leg, the leg may be interrupted to fly one or more butterfly patterns. Each butterfly consists of a minimum of two minutes straight/level that includes penetration of the feature followed by turns that allow re-penetration of the feature during the reciprocal part of the pattern.
- f) Where a defined layer of interest (such as a shallow layer of supercooled liquid water) is identified by the aircraft or radar, the long leg may be flown as a sawtooth leg with ascents/descents at 1000ft/min, extending 1000ft above and below the layer level (M.Sci may request level segments of 1 minute).
- g) Repeat items d) to e) as long as flight endurance or cloud conditions permit.
- h) End with below-cloud clear air aerosol leg (10 min) if possible, before recovering to destination airfield.

Sortie Detail B426b:

As B426a but in shortened form as directed by M.Sci with input from ground based sites

PROJECT BRIEF: APPRAISE-Clouds – mixed-phase cloud studies

Scientific Aims: The purpose of this project is to obtain detailed microphysical measurements in stratiform cloud systems, altocumulus clouds, wave clouds and cumulus clouds within the temperature regime in which ice particles will likely co-exist with liquid (typically 0 to -30C).

The flight plans are designed to characterise the aerosol above and below the cloud and infer aerosol fluxes into the cloud layer by combination with the vertical wind measurements and the microphysical characteristics within the cloud layer.

Constant altitude flight legs of approximately 50 km (10 minutes flying) will be made:

- In the boundary layer to measure the aerosol size distributions (from 10 nm to 100 um), CCN, aerosol composition from 30 nm to 1 um using the ToF AMS; larger particles and non-volatile material such as refractory material will be measured using EDAX analysis of filter samples.
- Near cloud base within cloud to measure the cloud droplets that have been activated from CCN, interstitial particles and larger particles that have fallen from cloud top. In addition the onset of ice will be observed using the CPI, CAPS and 2-D probes in cloud.
- Middle of the cloud passes will be made at temperatures where key processes will be expected to be initiated (-6C to -9C) for the Hallett-Mossop process or around -15C where fragmentation of dendritic crystals may be important.
- Near cloud top and within the cloud to measure entrainment and aerosols within entrained eddies and ice particles within the cloud; in colder clouds ice initiation will occur in this region.
- Above the cloud to measure the properties of aerosol particles that can potentially be entrained into the clouds.

In-situ measurements from the aircraft are performed in close coordination with the CAMRa radar and lidar facilities at Chilbolton, Hants.

Weather conditions: Stratiform, or altocumulus clouds lying over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility. This may or may not be generating precipitation at the surface. It is particularly desirable if the mean wind direction lies between about 220 and 280 degrees. This allows the aircraft to fly legs along the radar beam whilst staying closely parallel to the mean wind direction.

Key instruments and their operation.

Basic meteorology

- Rosemount temperatures, GE hygrometer, CR2
- GPS, GIN, turbulence probe – When in supercooled liquid water, Flight Manager or PIs should monitor turbulence probe calibrated differential pressures for signs of icing (cessation of variability on signal).

Cloud/Aerosol Physics/Chemistry

- FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, CDP. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits, appearance of large drops (>100micron) in 2D imagery when above freezing level.
- 2DS, CAPS and FSSP – as above
- J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC. Where a run is only partially in cloud and is starting in clear air, these should be zeroed/calibrated and a note made in the Flight Manager's log.
- TWC. If possible, a profile in clear air is desirable for calibration purposes.
- AMS, SMPS/WCPC (- to sample off both Rosemount and CVI inlets)
- Filters

CVI inlet sampling: residuals (and $Ly\alpha$) incloud; aerosols out of cloud (PCASP, CPC)

Mission Scientist Debrief: APPRAISE-Clouds: mixed-phase cloud studies:
Flight Number: B426, 28th Jan 2009 (Take-off 8:42 Landing 14:07)
Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To measure ice and liquid-phase microphysical processes in frontal clouds in association with the Chilbolton radar facility.

Weather conditions & operating area: A series of seasonal mid-latitude frontal systems had been crossing the UK from the west on previous days, and the latest of these was crossing over England and Wales during the early hours of Jan 28. The warm front associated with this was situated over central England (running from the Isle of White up to the North Yorkshire Coast) at midnight and this had earlier been expected to move only a little further eastward before being held up by the high pressure area sitting further to the east over northern Europe. Although the expected rate of progression of this system had changed a little in earlier forecasts, with the cold front following closely behind the warm front, all Met Office cloud models had forecasted there would be significant cloud cover at all levels over the whole of S England until late afternoon, with the level of precipitation over Chilbolton and to the west expected to diminish significantly from midday. The aim was to fly in this deep bank of cloud associated with the passage of the warm front and the approaching cold front. An early take-off at 09:00 was planned to enable either a double flight or a long single flight to be undertaken to study the system over and to the west of the Chilbolton radar facility.

Summary of the flight: The Met Office rainfall radar output showed that the edge of the main band of precipitation was clear of Chilbolton by about 07:00. Similarly the vertical pointing (35GHz) radar at Chilbolton (see 35GHz radar reflectivity factor figure for Jan 28 below) showed that the single deep cloud layer from the surface up to 9km associated with the warm front ceased to exist after 06:15 and was replaced by separate layers of low, middle and upper level cloud. It was thus clear before take-off that the passage of the warm front had speeded up so take-off time was brought forward to the earliest possible time of 08:42, and a single long flight (5hr 25min duration) was undertaken.

Met Office rainfall radar network 07:00

Cloud Base (CB) at take off was around 740ft. During the transit out to the operating area at FL100, the aircraft icing detection system detected a fair amount of liquid water in the cloud (at -9.5°C). Transiting further to the west, the plane first flew in cloud, then at cloud top (CT) (-8.25°C) and finally well above CT (-6.9°C) whilst flying at FL100. During the profile descent P1 (170° approach to Boscombe airfield) CT was encountered at 4.6kft (553mbar, 1.24°degC). At this time Chilbolton reported low, middle and high cloud layers (CTs at 8.8km, 5.2km and 2.2km respectively) over the observatory, each being around 1km deep (ie. CTs at 28.5kft, 17kft and 7.2kft). P1 was terminated at 2500ft and R1 started at that same level, which included a turn to the west to head out towards Exeter along a line parallel to the Chilbolton radial (255°) in cloud-free air. After 3.5minutes, profile ascent P2 was started on the same heading, interrupted briefly to move slightly further south. When the aircraft turned (short of the airlines running N-S

to west of Exeter) at the SW end of the Chilbolton radial (12.1kft/639mbar, -10.6°C), the air was still cloud-free. P2 was continued back towards Chilbolton (CH), and cloud bases were observed to be at around 14-16kft but the aircraft entered cloud first at around 18kft (506mbar, -23°C). CT was encountered at 22.8kft (413mbar, -36°C), and P2 continued on to FL250 (375mbar, -42°C), just short of CH. The radar facility reported turbulence in the layer near cloud top at 6000m (19.5kft), a possible indicator of the presence of liquid water. It was decided to investigate this upper level cloud by carrying out a series of straight and level runs (SLRs) in the cloud layer at successively lower altitudes. Firstly R2 was carried out (FL250) in the overhead over CH and in the turn over Pepis to the east and back over CH at the start of the outbound leg. The turn was carried out in intermittent cloud (as noted by the CVI). CT was variable (sometimes above, other times below FL250). 2DS started to report problems, but CPI saw a few bullet rosettes and CIP100 (PIP) reported some “blue splodges”.

Profile P3 down to FL190 was started soon after passing the CH overhead to investigate the turbulent layers. FL190 was reached 2/3 of the way along the outbound leg and SLR R3 started (484mbar, -26.7°C). R3 continued through the turn at the SW extreme and inbound back to CH. During R3, Chilbolton reported enhanced spectral width near CT in the lowest cloud layer (CT~2km) and that CT was flat. Later they reported the cloud layer at 2km was thinning. R3 was continued through the CH overhead and the turn at Pepis until passing back over CH, at which point a profile descent (P4) back down through the cloud was initiated. During the turn at Pepis, falling chunks of ice (around 400µm) were reported, CPI reported aggregates and 2DS started working properly again Chilbolton also reported ice falling into the cloud from higher level Cirrus above.

During P4 a cloud free layer was initially observed, but at 17.9kft, the aircraft was into cloud again (506mbar, -24.3°C). Liquid water was detected at 15.2kft (565mbar, -19.0°C), the 2DC observed “doughnuts” and CPI saw possible drops. Both the JW and Nevzorov probes saw liquid water too. At 13.7kft (~4.2km) the aircraft was through CB into cloud-free air (602mbar, -15.6°C). The latest satellite image uploaded showed cloud over CH, but thicker to the west and beyond. An RHI image from Chilbolton (below) confirmed this (the cloud layer being deepest from ~ 25km to 55km out on the radial from CH).

P4 continued on down through the turn at the SW end and back inbound to CH to try to enter the lower level cloud (CT reported by CH at 2km, 6.5kft). P4 was terminated at FL60 (810mbar, -0.92°C) and R4.1 started – initially in cloud free air. After 1 minute CT was seen below so R4.1 was stopped and a brief descent into cloud carried out. CT was encountered at 5.2kft (834mbar, -0.56°C) and R4.2 started at FL50 (841mbar, -0.29°C) in –cloud. JW and Nevzorov were seeing only liquid water now, core cloud saw nothing, FSSP saw small concentrations, while CAS saw $\sim 100\text{cm}^{-3}$ with a MVD of $15\mu\text{m}$. However the cloud was patchy and sunshine could be seen through the top at times. R4.2 was continued on through the CH overhead and the turn at Pepis during which 2DC saw drops. Chilbolton reported CT at 1.8km (5.9kft), and the latest RHI showed the upper cloud feature 25-30km out from CH persisting (at 10km CT/CB 6km/4km or 19.7/13kft, at 30km west 7km/4km or 23kft/13kft, with crystals at 8km seeding the layer below).

To maximize data coverage of the lower level cloud before returning to the higher ice cloud, it was decided to carry out a profile descent (P5) down through the low cloud layer to FL25 before profiling back up (ie a mini sawtooth). P5 was started on the outbound leg soon after passing CH. CB was encountered at 4.4kft (858mbar, 0.8°C) and another CT at 3.2kft (901mb, 3.3°C). P5 was terminated at FL25 (Portland p setting 1010mb) (2.6kft/919mbar, 3.3°C), and ascent profile P6 started immediately. At this point the FSSP concentration was $200\text{-}250\text{ cm}^{-3}$ while CDP saw 100 cm^{-3} and CAS $\sim 1000\text{ cm}^{-3}$ (mode at $15\text{-}20\mu\text{m}$ only). CT was seen at 3.7kft (884mbar, 1.9°C) and the next CB at 4.6kft (854mbar, 0.54°C). The high CAS numbers were considered OK, coinciding with much high LWC values on JW and Nev (5x higher than before at nearly 1g m^{-3}).

P6 was continued through the turn at the SW end of the radial. The latest radar plots confirmed the persistence of the upper level cloud (CB/CT 4km/7-7km; 13/19.5-23kft with falling ice from 7-8km; 26kft) and co-I Blyth requested investigation of the seeding ice particles. The bulk of the cloud was still 15-50km west of CH. At 17.8kft, it was clear the aircraft was in a gap in cloud (CB varying between $\sim 17\text{-}19\text{kft}$). P6 was terminated and R5.1 started (halfway back to CH) at FL200 (466mbar, -29.1°C). CB here was $\sim 17.5\text{kft}$ with CTs 1000-2000ft above FL200. CPI saw no evidence of liquid, 2DS saw aggregates, CIP saw crystals 300-400 μm in size)

Immediately before the CH overhead the aircraft ran out of cloud. 2DS started playing up again in the turn at Pepis. After passing overhead CH outbound, P7 was carried out up to FL210 and then R6.1 started so as to penetrate the CTs. The other imaging probes saw “clumpy ice” in the ascent. During R6.1 (445mbar, -31.5°C) core cloud reported constant concentrations of “small ice” and CPI saw small aggregates. Chilbolton reported interesting features at 5km (16.5kft) so the plan was to drop back down through the cloud on successive reciprocal runs doing a series of SLR legs. A pattern of dropping down to the next SLR level after the SW turn inbound and again after passing over CH outbound was instigated. SLRs R7.1, R8.1, R9.1, R10.1 and R11.1 preceded by profile descents P8, P9, P10, P11 and P12 were carried out (see table below; P = profile u/d: up/down).

P# u/d Run#	In/Out bound	(Final) Altitude	Pressure (mbar)	Temp (°C)	Comments
P8 d R7.1	I	FL200	464	-29.8	2DC larger crystals (500µm – previously 300µm)
P9 d R8.1	O	FL190	484	-27.0	
P10 d R9.1	I	FL170	525	-22.6	2DC # 2x, 600µm + some column/b.rosettes; CPI poss mixed phase, CIP&CAS see v small particles (15µm), CDP low concs of small things, 2DC seeing drops over CH end
P11 d R10.1	O	FL150	571	-18.0	
P12 d R11.1	I	FL130	618	-13.9	2DC mixture ice and water here, CPI sees aggregates + poss liquid
P13 u R12.1	O	FL140	595	-16.5	
P14 u R13.1	I	FL160	549	-20.0	Turn over Pepis – sunshine to south. Some bumps and gaps here
P15 u R14.1	O	FL180	506	-24.9	Climbed into cloud layer, R14.1 started in cloud
P16 u R15.1	I	FL200	486	-29.3	TWC reports Ci cleared through. All R15.1 above cloud layer
P17 d R16.1	O	FL190	484	-27.2	In and out of cloud as we go west
P18 d R17.1	I	FL170	526	-22.4	PCASP saw most counts yet 8 cm ⁻³ seem to be in gap – cloud to left and right, 2DC sees plates over CH

During R9.1 Chilbolton confirmed CB lowering over CH to 4km (13kft). TWC reported cloud continuing to descend, with CB ~3.5km. During P12 (FL150-FL130) the latest radar plots suggested CT ~5.5km (18kft) and CB (4.5km/14.7kft) lowering possibly to

3.5km (11.5kft) in places. However, during R11.1 MSci2 reported CB possibly lifting again slightly from 3.5km to 4-5.5km (13-18kft).

Following completion of R11.1 (FL130) (which was reportedly near CB) SLRs were continued but now stepping back up through the cloud layer filling in missing altitudes. R12.1, R13.1, R14.1 and R15.1, preceded by profile ascents P13, P14, P15, and P16 were carried out (as summarized above). Chilbolton reported cloud thinning (see below) as R13.1 was approaching CH, with CBs lifting from 4-5.5 km (13-18kft). It was also clear the cloud feature was advecting towards CH, so outbound runs R12.1 and R14.1 (and R16.1 later) were terminated earlier in order to be able to complete more SLR legs. Inbound leg R15.1 was carried out above cloud, so the final two SLRs, R16.1 and R17.1 were carried out following profile descents back into cloud. However by this stage the cloud was becoming very thin and difficult to capture on the Chilbolton radial. Science was completed following the end of R17.1 over CH. The aircraft returned was given clearance to transit back directly to Cranfield, landing at 14:07z.

Notes on instrumentation:

2DS – seemed to have difficulties running at the highest (coldest) altitudes

For full list of instrumentation functionality see flight log.

Final comments:

For more detailed information refer to Mission Scientist log sheets and screen dump file

Mission Scientist's Log [APPRAISE-CLOUDS] BS

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 1 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
8:30:50	(KNS)	8.32.44			Engine Stat (4-1) ✓ Rainy.
8:34.44		(KNS time = HDRAE + 42s)			Taxi (QNH 1013) 340'
8:42.17					Rolling 150/06 kt
8:42.46					T/O
		740ft			CB No rain ↑ 3500ft.
8:42:30	(Hovers) TRANS	FL100			[-9.42°/-6.6°C, 695mb, 4m/s/225°]
8:50.47	TRANS	FL100	242	52°18'/0°42'	A/C Anticong detected LW - fair amount
8:53.07	TRANS	FL100	243	52°12'/0°54'	CT, -8.25°/-7.54°, 695mb, 2m/s/221°
8:58.08	TRANS	FL100	245	52°0'/1°30'	Well above CT now (-6.92°/-9.72° 5m/s/321°)
09.06.06	PI start	8700	167	51°48'/1°42'	735mb, -4.07°/-7.21°C, 3m/s/10°
					↑ layers 2000 m = 6500
					5000 m = 16,400ft
					8000 m = 26,300ft
09.06.05	PI	46 kft	168	51°30'/1°36'	CT: 1.24°/1.14°C, 553mb, 3m/s/334°
9.06.12	PI end/R	2500ft	171	51°24'/1°36'	26 kft/920mb, 4.25°/5.04° 3m/s/267°
					[Cumulonimbus (CT's) @ 8,500m Δ 1000m = 26,500ft
		(out of cloud run)			5,200m Δ 1000m = 17,000ft
					2,200m Δ 1000m = 7,200ft
9.11.56	RI	2500'/26 kft	233	51°12'/1°30'	Right-Turn 3.52°/5.38°, 9m/s/267° 920mb.
		19,700 ←		CT	RHS - thicker cloud layer @ 30km = 6000 m
		13,100 ←		CT	4000 m
		26,300 ←		CT	@ 50 km (CT) = 8000 m
					↪ 19,500 CT - 13,100 ft layer
					CPI- LWC (CAS) making OK.
09.					

(RADSEARCH ⇒ out from CM layer 13-20,000 ft
13-26,000 ft)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
09.14.38	R1end/P2	2500ft	249	51°6'/1°42'	Cloud free run 920mb/26kft 4°44'/3.12° 8m/s/275
9.16.18	P2mb	3900ft	251	51°6'/1°54'	875mb, 1.97°/1.8°C, 7m/s/275°
9.17.41	P2res	3.9kft	250	51°0'/2°0'	to turn left + resume P2, 2.24°/1.25° 7m/s/270
9.19.38	P2	5.6kft	210	50°54'/2°6'	[Right turn] -0.69°/-1.46°C 3m/s/263 821mb
9.24.22	P2	10.1kft	262	50°54'/2°30'	[Still Cloud Free] -6.85°/20.2° 4m/s/293 692mb.
9.26.18	P2(RT)	12.1kft	260	50°48'/2°42'	(TWC + NB joined chut) -10.61°/33.6° 631mb
					- CB's starts 14000 - 16,000 approx
					(TWC - no flying tomorrow)
					-
					CB: 1.2 km level level (4000')
					4km middle layer (13100')
					67 km upper layer (20-23000')
9.32.10	P2	18,000	70	50°54'/2°24'	In Cloud; -23.09°/-25.06° 506mb, 5m/s/331°
9.35.21	P2	21.2kft	75	51°0'/2°0'	442mb -31.95°/30.73° 3m/s/226°
					MSc2: Middle cloud 4000-7000m
					turbulence → in layer near top may ⇒ liquid water
					(B - 10500 ft ≡ 4000-6000m)
9.36.56	P2	22.8kft	76	51°0'/1°48'	CT; -35.94°/34.23°C 413mb, 7m/s/214°
					CT sloping up to NW of us....
					MSc - Radar data - gross 2-4km....
9.39.22	P2end/P2	FL250	76	51°6'/1°30'	375mb -42.04°/43.92° 8m/s/220°
9.40.5	R2	FL250	76	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH & turning -42.02°/44.76° 8m/s/225° (Hazy again)
					2DS - Bullet Rosettes on CH
					DIP - "Blue Sidges"
					CVI - In and out of cloud on turn? - yes /

CH

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 3 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Cloud is patchy here - some CT's ↑
					[ie CT variable] some CT's below.
09.43.54	R2	FL250	275	51°6'/1°6'	In Cloud 375mb -41.86°/-42.59° 12m/s/225°
09.46.02	R2	FL250	245	51°6'/1°24'	CH ON 375mb -41.13°/-43.12 12m/s/213°
09.46.10	R2 end / R3	FL250	246	51°6'/1°24'	descending into ^{mount} cloud - hopechilly.
09.49.22	P3 ↓	22.2M	245	51°0'/1°48'	423mb -34.7°/-35.62° 10m/s/224°
09.49.53	P3 #	21.7M	239	51°0'/1°54'	Inc descent rate ATC - CT -33.61°/-33.4°, 433mb.
09.50.10	P3 ↓	21.0M	240	51°0'/1°54'	Normal descent rate again now. -32.11°/-30.26 445mb.
09.52.10	P3 / R3	FL190	256	51°0'/2°6'	484mb -26.75°/-26.09° 7m/s/247°
09.54.10	R3	FL190	256	50°54'/2°18'	hole in cloud below LMB -26.85°/-27.5°, 484.
		6500 ←			MSc - LW? 6000m Holes
		6500' ←			lowest layer CT, 2000m - flat
					(with enhanced spectral width)
9.55.15	R3	FL190	254	50°54'/2°30'	turning for recip' now. -26.91°/-26.62 4m/s/268°
10.03.54	R3	FL190	75	51°0'/1°42'	484mb -26.71°/-23.84° 4m/s/243°
					Upper layer clear on radar plots now.
10.05.01	R3	FL190	75	51°6'/1°36'	484mb -26.53°/-25.96° 5m/s/252°
					Falling ice - about 400µm - reported
					CPI - aggregates
					2DS - working now again
					RADSSR CH - 2km layer thinning now.
10.06.26	R3	FL190	76	51°6'/1°24'	CH CH, -26.41°/-26.02° 484mb 7m/s/242°
10.08.02	R3	FL190	64	51°6'/1°12'	forming at PEPIS -26.13°/-25.79° 7m/s/233°
10.08.35	R3	FL190	121	51°6'/1°6'	CH reports falling ice from Cirrus overhead

CPI sees aggregates, core cloud says 400µm vs 5µm
(-25.96°/-26.27° 485mb 7m/s/207°)

CH

CH

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 4 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
10:12:32	R3ew/R4	FL190	253	51°6'/1°24'	484mb -26.66°/-24.85° 10m/s/233°
10:13:40	P4	17.9kft	254	51°6'/1°36'	in cloud again -24.38°/-22.28° 506mb 10m/s/215°
10:16:22	P4	15.2kft	256	51°0'/1°54'	LW- 2DC "doughnuts" } -19.04°/-18.56° CPI poss drops } 565mb JW/New sees LW too } 7m/s/275°
10:18:10	P4	13.7kft	256	51°0'/2°0'	Through CB - into gap now 602mb -15.57°/-23.56° 5m/s/294° Sink image 9.45 Cloud cur over CH - thicker to west and beyond - as R41 shows too.
10:22:27	P4	10.2kft	255	50°54'/2°30'	Duration Right -6.35°/-21.21° 2m/s/320 69 Smb.
10:25:23	P4	7.2kft	96	50°54'/2°24'	- can see ice and cloud probes on JW (* - Nov (-2.27°/-4.37° 774mb 2m/122°)
10:26:50	R4end/R4.1	6.0kft	69	50°54'/2°15'	810mb -0.92°/-1.31° 3m/s/298°
10:27:53	R4.1end	FL60	75	51°/2°12'	810mb above CT - so descend into cloud.
10:29:13	descent	5.2kft	71	51°/2°0'	CT 834mb -0.56°/+0.03° 4m/s/329°
10:29:34	R4.2st	FL50	70	51°/2°0'	in cloud. 841mb -0.24°/+0.23° 4m/s/331 JW/New - LW only now Grey Cloud - subtle - PSSP small ones only CAS # ~ 100 cm ³ MVD ~ 15um - Cloud patchy - see sunshine at Kms
10:34:37	R4.2	FL50	75	51°6'/1°30'	Make in CT, back in again -0.3°/0.02° 842mb
10:35:35	R4.2	FL50	72	51°6'/1°24'	CH CH -0.24°/+0.29° 842mb 6m/s/307° 2DC - seeing liquid drops

(* = pulses.)

CH

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 5 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
		4900 5900 ft			Updates: 1.8 km ² CT 300-350 m thick = CB 1.5 km
					RMI scan - feature 25-30 km - persisting 4-5 km OK ✓
					Radsearch
(Copied down)					
CH 10:35:35	R4.2	FL50	72	51°6'/1°24'	OH CH -0.24°/0.29°C 6m/s/307 842mb. at FL - cloud 300m thick e 10km - 6km } (19,700 ft) 4km } (13,100 ft) 30km West 7km } (23,000 ft) 4km } (13,000 ft) Xbands pass at 8km - seeding layer below ??
CH 10:41:02	R4.2	FL50	244	51°6'/1°24'	841mb -0.35°/0.36° 5m/s/275
10:41:16	R4.2 and / PS	FL50	246	51°6'/1°24'	841mb -0.47°/0.35° 5m/s/270
10:42:09	PS	4.4kft	260	51°6'/1°30'	CB. 859mb 0.8°/1.05°C 6m/s/278°
					1010 Portland -
10:43:44	PS	3.2kft	253	51°/1°36'	CT. 3.2kft (on Portland 1010 mb) 3.31°/1.46°C 901mb
10:44:30	PS/P6	2.6kft	255	51°/1°42'	919mb 3.34°/4.53°C 6m/s/256° PSSP. 200-250 cm ³ CDP 100 cm ² CAS ~ 1000 - peaks 2µm - 15-20µm only
10:44:53	P6	3.7kft	256	51°/1°48'	CT at 1000m cloud? 1.91°/3.88° 884mb
10:47:04	P6	4.6kft	255	51°/1°54'	CB 854mb 0.54°/1.37° 5m/s/271°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. Bowen Page A of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					High conv in CAS true....
					LWC - all probes much higher than Sx (Jw, Nav)
10.53.06	P6				- continue ascent to middle layer CT or P200
					A Blyk - request investigations of particles at 7-8 km - falling into layer below.
					RMI scan - see feature AB integrated in
10:54.57	P6	12.4kft	254	50°54'/2°42'	Turn at SW corner. -12.41°/25.13° 633mb
					From RMI plots:-
					layer - 4km ≡ 13,000ft
					CT 6km → 7km ≡ 19,600-23000ft
					Falling ice 7-8km ≡ 26,000ft
					Bull ^d cloud 15-50 km West CN....
10.59.39	P6	17.8kft	71°	50°54'/2°16'	Gap in cloud (~17-19kft) -24.1°/-24.6° 509mb. Base 170-
11.01.54	P6 end/ RS.1	P200	72°	51°/2°6'	19.9kft / 466mb, -29.05/-28.82°C 2m/s/315 C Base ~ 17.5kft Tops ~ 1000-2000' above us
					Doug - Blue Sky over Exeter - great.
					No evidence LW (CPI) last run
					ZDS - very regular
					CIP - 300-2000m
					RMI - persistent 4km-6km (occ 7km)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 7 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11.06.46	RS.1	FL200	74°	51°6'/1°30'	Out of cloud here. -28.93°/-28.89°C 465mb
11.07.33	RS.1	FL200	69°	51°6'/1°24'	On CR, 465mb -28.76°/-30.35° 3mb/262°
11.09.01	RS.1	FL200	66°	51°6'/1°12'	Paper burn. -28.49°/-28.55 5mb/241 465mb
					another RHI - dumped.
					CPI - 2DS playing up again
11.13.19	P7st	FL200	253	51°6'/1°24'	465mb -28.97°/-28.31° 7mb/230°
					Core cloud - just seeing "dumpy ice"
					CPI - 2DS
11.14.27	P7st/R6.1	FL210	255	51°6'/1°36'	445mb -31.49°/-32.38° 7mb/239°
					Core cloud - consist small ice here
					CPI - small aggregated
					Radsearch - 5km and below - interclouds
					features (16400ft - great!).
					So will drop down at 1000ft intervals
					near CT. here.
11.23.22	R6.1	FL210	254	50°54'/2°36'	turn 446mb -32.28°/-32.09° 5mb/241
11.25.35	R6.1/P8	FL210	117	50°54'/2°36'	In and out CT's -32.38°/-32.74 1mb/252 445mb
11.26.45	P6/R7.1	FL200	88	50°54'/2°24'	464mb -29.83°/-30.06 1mb/324°
11.35.34	R7.1	FL200	71	51°6'/1°24'	On CR -29.15°/-29.35° 4mb/260 464mb
					Core cloud 2DC - seeing slight larger Xcls 500µm
					300µm - primarily -

(35 mins per 2000 runs

5.1 11.09)

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 426 Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 8 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11.41.18	R7end/P9	FL200	250	51°6'/1°24'	464mb -29.19°/-29.01 0m/s/241'
11.42.28	P7end/R8.1	FL190	255	51°6'/1°36'	484mb -27.04°/-26.51 4m/s/245'
11.52.27	R8.1/P10	FL190			
11.54.09	P10	18.5W	121	50°54'/2°36'	turn 495mb -26.29°/-26.42 2m/s/332°
11.55.32	P10/R9.1	F170	79	50°54'/2°30'	525mb -22.55°/-23.76 5m/s/327°
					CH - cirrus CB - thickens @ 4km (13,000ft)
					Core Cloud - patch 2x cres 600µm some cirrus/bellies too.
					CIF - mixed phase possible !! - very small 15µm at low on CIP - CAS
					CDP - picking up low cres of small things
12.05.04	R9.1	FL170	68	51°6'/1°18'	CH CH 526mb -22.41°/-19.71° (4m/s/259°)
					all LW seen blips - gone now
					2DC - now seeing drops !!
					Two - very interesting - wrote PHD on that!
12.06.28	R9.1	FL170	69	51°6'/1°12'	Pep's 526mb -22.3°/-20.93 4m/s/259°
12.10.15	R9.1	FL170	248	51°6'/1°24'	CH CH, 526mb -22.5°/-20.15°C 5m/s/226°
12.10.27	R9.1end/P11	FL170	249	51°6'/1°24'	526mb. -22.59°/-20.85° 5m/s/229°
					last Sc - more cirrus in this area - below us.
					Two -
					Rad reflector - continues to descend - CB 3km now.
12.12.36	P11end/R10.1	FL150	256	51°/1°42'	571mb -17.97°/-19.56°C 7m/s/296°

(8.35 - 14.03)

mv'd 3-400µm on CIP
Core den 200-250µm > still sun

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 426 Date 28/01/09 Name R. N. BOWEN Page 9 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
12.22.09	R10.1	FL150	256	50°54'/2°42'	turn 571mb -18.11°C/-20.01°C 5mbs/282°
12.23.03	R10.1 ex P12	F150	358	50°54'/2°42'	571mb -18.19°C/-19.79°C 7mbs/298
					CT 5500m (18,000ft)
					CB [Ice] 4500m pass lower 3500m (14,700ft or 11500ft)
					(lower level at 2km too) (6500ft)
12.24.56	P12 ex/ R11.1	FL160	111	50°54'/2°36'	618mb -13.88/-25.41°C 3mbs/333°
					AMS-labeled R11 on Plate a
					Missing - CB tilted slightly - CB 3.5km now ↑
					S.S - 4km (18,000-13000ft)
					CB - just below 4km - M&Z
12.35.35	R11.1	FL130	71	51°6'/1°24'	On CB -13.91°/-17.74° 10mbs/325° 618mb
					One cloud - mixture ice + water here.
					CB - ice - aggregates
12.38.10	R11.1				OP1 - pass again LW drop ear too
12.39.58	R11.1	FL130	295	51°6'/1°12'	(Pops?) -13.91°/-17.04° 618mb 7mbs/305.
12.42.40	R11.1/ P13	FL130	257	51°6'/1°30'	618mb -13.65°/-18.65° 7mbs/315°
12.43.49	P13/ R12.1	FL140	259	51°0'/1°36'	595mb -16.54°/-17.95° 6mbs/303°
12.48.57	R12.1/ P14	FL140	256	50°54'/2°12'	594mb, -16.48°/-20.96° 4mbs/292°
12.50.01	P14	FL130	267	50°54'/2°18'	Right turn -18.18°/-16.88° 7mbs/290 571mb
12.51.06	P14/ R13.1	FL160	31	51°0'/2°18'	549mb, -20.0°/-21.87° 7mbs/332°
					OH - Cloud thinning CB 4km S.S. 1km CT.

CH

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....⁴²⁶ Date 28/01/09 Name K.N. BOWER Page 10 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					overhead Rad CB ~ 4km - 5.5 (13-18kt)
					→ mist of cloud is much closer (only now)
					to Chubbatten now
12.56.32	R13.1	FL160	71	51°/1°42'	Into Cloud Patch here -20.54/-20.37° 548mb (Pony Qs: ETA R Pete Chappell = 16.05) 1 or 2 flights = 1
12.59.36	R13.1	FL160	72	51°6'/1°24'	On CH 548mb -20.44/-19.33 4m/s/355
13.01.29	R13.1	FL160	66	51°12'/1°12'	Right turn - Pepsi 548mb -20.14/-20.1 4m/s/370 Sunshine on LHS - few burns too! Now in gaps
13.03.44	R13.1/P13	FL160	236	51°6'/1°24'	Climbed into cloud layer -20.41/-19.71 549mb (0-mb)
13.07.43	P13cont/ R14	FL150	256	51°/1°36'	506mb -24.89/-23.25°C 506mb 1m/s/206° Stated in cloud
13.13.16	R14.1cont/ P16	FL150	261	50°54'/2°18'	Turning, 505mb -24.81/-25.32° 3m/s/288° Two - into Ci - cleared through!
13.15.32	P16/ Stab	R15.1 FL200	122	51°/2°12'	486mb -29.32/-29.8°C 1m/s/292° Odds & ends of ice → All PCT here
13.22.29	R15.1	FL200	75	51°6'/1°24'	On CH - 465mb -28.94/-30.72° 1m/s/264°
13.24.13	R15.1	FL200	77	51°6'/1°12'	turning at PEMPIS -29.02/-30.06° 483mb * all but run above CT. * cloud below is very thin
13.27.40	R15.1cont/ P7	FL200	250	51°6'/1°24'	465mb ~ On CH. -29.02/-31.14° 5m/s/210°
13.28.55	P17cont/ R16.1	FL190	256	51°6'/1°30'	484mb, -27.24/-25.97°C 2m/s/242° into cloud and then out of it again - as we go west - cloud

A/c anti icing - fair amount LW

Out of CT

Well above CT now

Turn for Boscome

start P1 down

CT

End P1 start R1 2500ft

Right turn

End R1 (cloud free) start P2

P2 int

Turn and P2 res

P2 turn

Still cloud free

Right turn

P2 18000

CT

End P2 start R2

OH CH and turning

In cloud - variable cloud tops

OH CH R2

End R2 start P3

Increasing descent rate - in cloud

Resume standard descent rate

End P3 start R3

Hole in cloud below LHS

Turning for recip run

OH CH turning for Pepis

Turning at Pepis

Ch reports ice falling from Ci overhead - CPI sees agg, core 400um ice

R3 end P4 start

In cloud again

Latest 4 hours

Today

2DC doughnuts, CPI poss drops, JW Nev LW too

CB - into cloud free gap now

Turning

End P4 start R4.1

above CT, R4.1 end descend to

CT

Start R4.2 at FL50

Hole just out CT then in again

OH CH

OH CH

end R4.2 start P5

CB

CT on 1010 portland

End P5 start P6

CT

CB

Right turn at SW end

Gap in cloud 17-19000

P6 R5.1

Out of cloud

OH CH

Pepis Turn

Start P7

End P7 start R6.1

turn

End R6.1 Start P8

End P8 start R7.1

OH CH

EVUK71 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 28 Jan 2009 1045 UTC

Flight Summary B426

Event	Start	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Stop	Hdg	Hgt	Lat	Long	Comment
Start-Up	08:31:58	306	0.36kft	52.1N	0.6W						
taxy	08:34:09	306	0.36kft	52.1N	0.6W						
T/O	08:42:05	211	0.37kft	52.1N	0.6W						
Profile 1	09:01:14	168	8.5kft	51.9N	1.8W	09:08:20	171	2.6kft	51.4N	1.6W	
run 1.1	09:08:28	171	2.6kft	51.4N	1.6W						
run 1.1	09:14:09	248	2.6kft	51.2N	1.7W						end
Profile 2	09:14:39	249	2.6kft	51.1N	1.8W	09:39:21	076	25.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Profile 2	09:16:31	251	4.0kft	51.1N	1.9W						interrupt
Profile 2	09:17:42	250	4.0kft	51.1N	2.0W						resume
jw/nevz zero	09:19:07	210	5.2kft	51.0N	2.1W						
cpc logging	09:21:20	260	7.1kft	50.9N	2.3W						started
Run 2.1	09:39:28	076	25.1kft	51.1N	1.6W	09:42:08	087	25.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
ovhd	09:40:31	071	25.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chil
Profile 3	09:46:11	246	25.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	09:52:12	255	19.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Run 3.1	09:52:12	255	19.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	09:55:28	264	19.0kft	50.9N	2.5W	
Run 3.2	10:04:42	075	19.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	10:07:59	064	19.0kft	51.2N	1.3W	at 100000
ovhd	10:06:28	075	19.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 4	10:12:34	254	19.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	10:26:51	070	6.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Run 4.1	10:26:52	070	6.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	10:27:55	075	6.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Run 4.2	10:29:36	071	5.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	10:37:19	063	5.0kft	51.2N	1.3W	
ovhd	10:35:43	071	5.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 5	10:41:16	248	5.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	10:44:30	255	2.6kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Profile 6	10:44:30	255	2.6kft	51.1N	1.7W	11:01:56	072	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	
Run 5.1	11:01:56	072	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	11:09:00	066	20.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 7	11:13:21	253	20.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	11:14:29	255	21.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	

End R7 start P9

End P9 start R8.1

SW turn

End P10

OH CH

Pepis

OH CH

End R9.1 start P11

End P11 start R10.1

EVUK71 MSG High Resolution Visible Image 28 Jan 2009 1045 UTC

turn

End R10.1 start P12

End P12 start R11.1

Latest 4 hours

Today

OH CH be low or at CB

End R11.1 Start P13

end P13 start R12.1

End R12.1 start P14

Right turn

P14 end start R13.1

Into cloud here - patch

OH CH

Pepis right turn

End R13.1 start P15

End P15 start R14.1

Run 3.2	10:04:42	075	19.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	10:07:59	064	19.0kft	51.2N	1.3W	at 100000
ovhd	10:06:28	075	19.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 4	10:12:34	254	19.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	10:26:51	070	6.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Run 4.1	10:26:52	070	6.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	10:27:55	075	6.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Run 4.2	10:29:36	071	5.0kft	51.0N	2.0W	10:37:19	063	5.0kft	51.2N	1.3W	
ovhd	10:35:43	071	5.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 5	10:41:16	248	5.1kft	51.1N	1.5W	10:44:30	255	2.6kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Profile 6	10:44:30	255	2.6kft	51.1N	1.7W	11:01:56	072	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	
Run 5.1	11:01:56	072	20.0kft	51.0N	2.1W	11:09:00	066	20.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 7	11:13:21	253	20.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	11:14:29	255	21.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 6.1	11:14:29	255	21.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	11:25:41	120	21.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	
Profile 8	11:25:41	120	21.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	11:26:47	088	20.0kft	51.0N	2.5W	
Run 7.1	11:26:47	088	20.0kft	51.0N	2.5W	11:37:12	084	20.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 9	11:41:22	250	20.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	11:42:33	256	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 8.1	11:42:33	256	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	11:52:27	317	19.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 10	11:53:14	035	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	11:55:32	079	17.1kft	50.9N	2.5W	
Run 9.1	11:55:33	078	17.1kft	50.9N	2.5W	12:06:30	075	17.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 11	12:10:26	248	17.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	12:12:42	256	15.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 10.1	12:12:42	256	15.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:22:51	336	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 12	12:23:04	358	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:25:09	098	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Run 11.1	12:25:09	098	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	12:42:42	256	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
ovhd	12:35:52	068	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 13	12:42:43	256	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	12:43:59	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 12.1	12:43:59	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:49:12	255	14.2kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Profile 14	12:49:12	255	14.2kft	51.0N	2.2W	12:51:12	041	16.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 13.1	12:51:13	041	16.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	13:05:44	236	16.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
ovhd	12:59:38	072	16.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 15	13:05:44	236	16.0kft	51.1N	1.5W						

Turning end R14.1 start P16

Just before end P16 start

Just after start R15.1

OH CH

Turning at Pepis

End R15.1 start P 17 then OH CH

End P17 start R16.1 FL190

End R16.1 start P18

End P18 start R17.1 at FL170

OH CH

End or R17.1

Profile 7	11:13:21	253	20.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	11:14:29	255	21.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 6.1	11:14:29	255	21.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	11:25:41	120	21.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	
Profile 8	11:25:41	120	21.0kft	51.0N	2.6W	11:26:47	088	20.0kft	51.0N	2.5W	
Run 7.1	11:26:47	088	20.0kft	51.0N	2.5W	11:37:12	084	20.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 9	11:41:22	250	20.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	11:42:33	256	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 8.1	11:42:33	256	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	11:52:27	317	19.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 10	11:53:14	035	19.0kft	51.0N	2.8W	11:55:32	079	17.1kft	50.9N	2.5W	
Run 9.1	11:55:33	078	17.1kft	50.9N	2.5W	12:06:30	075	17.0kft	51.2N	1.2W	
Profile 11	12:10:26	248	17.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	12:12:42	256	15.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 10.1	12:12:42	256	15.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:22:51	336	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	
Profile 12	12:23:04	358	15.0kft	50.9N	2.8W	12:25:09	098	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	
Run 11.1	12:25:09	098	13.0kft	50.9N	2.6W	12:42:42	256	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
ovhd	12:35:52	068	13.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 13	12:42:43	256	13.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	12:43:59	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 12.1	12:43:59	259	14.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	12:49:12	255	14.2kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Profile 14	12:49:12	255	14.2kft	51.0N	2.2W	12:51:12	041	16.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	
Run 13.1	12:51:13	041	16.0kft	51.0N	2.4W	13:05:44	236	16.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	
ovhd	12:59:38	072	16.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 15	13:05:44	236	16.0kft	51.1N	1.5W	13:07:44	256	18.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	
Run 14.1	13:07:44	256	18.0kft	51.1N	1.7W	13:13:20	261	18.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Profile 16	13:13:20	261	18.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	13:15:39	117	20.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	
Run 15.1	13:15:40	117	20.0kft	51.0N	2.3W	13:27:41	250	20.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
ovhd	13:22:26	075	20.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb
Profile 17	13:27:42	249	20.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	13:28:57	258	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	
Run 16.1	13:28:57	258	19.0kft	51.1N	1.6W	13:34:38	254	19.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	
Profile 18	13:34:38	254	19.0kft	51.0N	2.2W	13:36:45	106	17.0kft	51.1N	2.2W	
Run 17.1	13:36:45	106	17.0kft	51.1N	2.2W	13:44:28	076	17.0kft	51.1N	1.4W	
ovhd	13:44:06	077	17.0kft	51.1N	1.4W						chilb

New plot, same times

Flight B426 13:53:01
Heading 30 deg Speed 280 knots Height 9.0kft Press 723mb
Lat 51°42.0'N Long 0°54.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 351 deg
Temp -3.7C Dewpoint -12.15C
From 08:42:00 to now

Current values

—	TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	49980	secs	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	All	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	sc
—	JW LIQUID WATER CONTENT	-0.02	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			
—	NEVZOROV LIQUID WATER	0.01	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			
—	NEVZOROV TOTAL WATER	0	g m-3	<input type="radio"/>			

Cloud Physics Flight Log B426

Date: 28/01/09	Operator: KFT	DRS Time: 07:12	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: N/A	AUX1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time:+0
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	PCASP		2DC		2DP		CDP		FFSSP		UMan FSSP		PIP	
Operated?	Y		Y		N		Y		Y		Y		Y	
Pre-flight checks	Vref:(>7.0)*	4.45	E#11:(>1.0)	2.0	EI#1:(>1.0)		Laser V:	2.7	Ref V:	3.5	Ref V:	9.1	EI#1 V:	1.66
	Flow:	0.92	EI#32:(>1.0)	1.9									EI#32 V:	3.32
	T (°C)	4.4											EI#64 V:	2.56
	P (hPa)	999					TAS set	PIP						

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP		CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size		Blocks Tx	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC		
08:43																		PCASP using FSSP card
08:57																	DAT	DAT measured
09:01:08	FL100	2	0.06	0	0				63	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:01:55	FL080	7	0.08	0	0				63	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:02:13	FL070	1	0.06	0	0				63	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:04:40	FL060	0	0.00	0	0				63	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:05:36	FL050	0	0.05	0	0				63	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
09:06:40	FL040	3	0.17	30	200			11	88	35	12	75	25	0	0	0	0	
09:06:12	FL025	38	0.18	75	375			1	134	106	12	100	22	0.02	20	0.09		Static p +30mb from a/c
09:10:00		40	0.13	4	400			1	321	100	11	120	20	0.035				T also suspect
09:14:00		6	0.09	0	0				463	50	14	0	0	0	0			
09:14:50		5	0.07	0	0				463	0		0		0				Start profile
09:16:21	FL040	2	0.08	0	0				463	0		0		0				
09:20:05	FL060	1	0.06	0	0				463	0		0		0				
09:21:22	FL070	2	0.07	0	0				463	5	5	0		0				
09:22:20	FL080	2	0.06	0	0				463	0		0		0				
09:23:20	FL090	6	0.07	0					463	0		0		0				
09:25:15	FL110	1	0.06	0					463	0		0		0				
09:27:13	FL130	2	0.08	0					463	0		0		0				
09:28:18	FL140	8	0.08	7	500			8	463	0	45	0	30	0.02	1000	0.02		
09:29:20	FL150	2	0.14	14	525			11	464	0		0		0.015	1500			
09:31:12	FL170	0	0.05	2	700			8	464	0		0		0.01	1000			

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
09:33:00	FL190	2	0.25	50	650			8	466	NOISE	?	0.05	30	0.005	500		
09:34:18	FL200	11	0.46	48	650			8, 4	469	NOISE		0.05	30	0.005	500		
09:37:07	FL230	0		0					474	NOISE		0		0			
09:38:00	FL240	0		0						0		0		0			
09:39:28	FL250	0		19	250			4,8,11	474	NOISE		0	25	0.005	21		Start run
09:42:00	FL250	30	0.50	137	350			4	476	NOISE		0	28	0.01	1000		
09:44:00		1	0.032	33	400			4, 11	478	NOISE		0		0			
09:46:11		1	0.17	14	525			5,4,11	479	NOISE		0		0			START PROFILE 3
09:47:12	FL240	0		0					479	0		0		0			
09:48:33	FL230	9	0.52	16	250			8,11	479	NOISE		0		0.005	500		
09:49:30	FL220	25	0.30	30	500			8,4	480	NOISE		1	28	0.015	2500		
09:50:11	FL210	69	0.23	175	425			8	484	NOISE		0.5	28	0.01	2000		
09:51:12	FL200	18	0.40	70	775			4,11,8	488	NOISE		0.4	28	0.007	2000		
09:52:03	FL190	21	0.27	51	700			4,8,11	491	NOISE		0.5	28	0.005	1500		
09:54:00	FL190	2	0.17	38	325			5,8	494	NOISE		0.5	25	0.01	214		
09:56:00		7	0.38	79	450			8	496	NOISE		0.2	28	0.01	57	0.01	
09:58:00		3	0.27	69	400			8,11	498	NOISE		0.1	28	0.01	2500	0.04	
10:00:00		83	0.26	77	625			4,8	504	NOISE		0.8	28	0.01	4430	2.12	
10:04:00	FL190	0		13	500			4,8	516	NOISE		0.1	32	0	230	0.02	
10:08:00				0					517	0		0		0	550	0	
10:12:00		0		0					517	0		0		0			
10:13:28	FL180	3	0.41	24	650			4,5,8	518			5	28	0	1080	0.22	PROFILE 4
10:14:31	FL170	16	0.41	8	600			4,5, 8,12	519			5	30	0.005	800	0.52	
10:16:35	FL150	6	0.26	80	750			4,8,12	525			5	30	0.02	800	1.28	
10:17:30	FL140	6	0.13	4	625			12,4,8	527	NOISE		1	30	0.01	500		Airspeed 10m/s ICED!
10:20:10	FL120	3	0.08	0					527	0		0		0			
10:22:28	FL100	22	0.08	0					527	0		0		0			
10:24:27	FL080	3	0.08	0					527	0		0		0			
10:25:36	FL070	5	0.06	0					527	0		0		0			
10:26:53	FL060	1	0.07	0					527	0		0		0			RUN 4
10:29:36	FL050	22	0.18	0					539	25	9	30	18	0			PIP Airspeed 90m/s
10:32:00		4	0.08	0					568	5	3	30	15	0			
10:35:00		9	0.20	0					632	20	9	40	18	0			
10:36:00		50	0.21	81	175			12	646	20	5	20	18	0.006	?		T<0
10:39:00		26	0.22	225	75			12	676	15	15	20	18	0.005	?		
10:41:00	FL050	21	0.25	1	75			12	705	10	5	18	18	0			SAWTOOTHES
10:42:40	FL040	10	0.07	0					714	0		0		0			

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
10:44:00	FL030	16	0.07	1	250			12	736	100	5	150	18	0		2.5	PROFILE UP
10:46:15	FL040	4	0.08	0					904	0		0		0		2.5	
10:47:40	FL050	0		0					912	0		0		0			
10:48:33	FL060	0		0					912	0		0		0			
10:57:00	FL150	0	0.08	0					912	0		0		0	400	1.3	
10:58:00	FL160	2	0.35	33	400			8	913	0.02	25	5	10	0			
10:59:54	FL180	2	0.06	8	250			11	913	0.02	35	0		0	0		
11:00:51	FL190	2	0.06	0					913	0		0		0			
11:01:58	FL200	3	0.21	36	325			8	914			5	8	0.008	250	1	
11:05:00	FL200	100	0.21	40	650			8	919	NOISE		5	8	0.005	500	1.02	RUN 5.1
11:08:00		1	0.05	0					919	0		0		0			
11:12:00	FL200	3	0.06	0					919	0		0		0			
11:14:00	FL200	3	0.18	2	425			8,11	920	0		0		0.004	100		
11:16:00	FL210	1	0.06	4	350			8,11	921	NOISE		0		0.003	100	1	
11:18:00	FL210	2	0.09	40	225			8,11	922	0		0		0.001	100	1	
11:20:00	FL210	1	0.11	37	175			8,11	923	NOISE		0		0.003	0	1	
11:22:00	FL210	3	0.12	18	325			8,11	924	0		0		0			
11:24:00	FL210	1	0.10	19	375			8,5,4	924	NOISE		0		0.003	200	1.05	
11:26:47	FL200	10	0.55	31	325			8,11	925	NOISE		0		0.004	50	1.1	START RUN
11:29:00	FL200	11	0.07	36	275			8,11	926	0		0		0			
11:31:00	FL200	6	0.30	9	325			8,11	927	0		0		0.007	200		
11:33:00	FL200	2	0.11	5	300			8,11	927	NOISE		0		0.004	0	1.1	
11:36:00	FL200	0		0					929	0		0		0			
11:39:00	FL200	2	00.05	2	250			8,11	929	0		0		0.016	2200	1.15	
11:42:30	FL190	1	0.31	32	375			8,11	930	0		0		0.004	200		PROFILE 9
11:46:00	FL190	9	0.29	46	325			8,11	932	0		2	8	0.003	200	1.25	
11:48:00	FL190	11	0.07	48	350			8,11	933	0		1	7	0.001	0		
11:58:00	FL170	5	0.06	2	450			8,11	934	0		1	8	0.008	100	1.6	
12:00:00	FL170	11	0.37	56	550			8	936	0		5	8	0.03	3000	1.7	
12:02:00	FL170	3	0.10	3	650			8	937	0		1	8	0.001	500		
12:04:00	FL170	4	0.10	18	650			8,4	938	NOISE		5	9	0.002	450		
12:06:00	FL170	15	0.13	64	675			8,4,12	945	4	25	18	12	0.003	400		T=MS22
12:10:00	FL170	3	0.41	11	775			8,12,4	953	0		2	8	0.001	500		
12:11:30	FL160	12	0.09	10	750			8,4,12	954	0		1	8	0.002	450		PROFILE 11
12:12:42	FL150	8	0.10	27	475			8,12,4	955	0		1	8	0.015	250		

GMT	Height	PCASP		2DC		2DP		Habit	FFSSP Blocks Tx	CDP		UMan FSSP		PIP			Comments
		#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max size	#/m ³	Max size			#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	LWC	
12:16:00	FL150	3	0.07	5	250			8,12	957	0		0		0			
12:18:00	FL150	13	0.06	19	250			5,8,12	957	0		1	8	0.007	0		
12:20:00	FL150	11	0.07	0.5	225			11,12	957	0		0		0			
12:22:00	FL150	3	0.07	0					957	0		0		0			
12:25:00	FL130	1	0.07	0					957	0		0		0			DAT OBSERVED
12:28:00	FL130	6	0.08	0					957	0		0		0			
12:30:00	FL130	3	0.17	0					957	0		0		0			PIP AIRSPEED 10m/s
12:34:00	FL130	12	0.08	0					958	0		0		0			
12:36:00	FL130	3	0.11	7	300			11,12	958	0		0		0.001	0		
12:38:30	FL130	5	0.23	48	600			8,12	960	2	5	4	8	0.03	600		PIP IMAGES STRANGE Seeing horizontal dashes
12:40:00	FL130	1	0.05	8	450			8	962	0		0		0			
12:43:53	FL140	1	0.10	18	500			8	962	0.5	5	1	7	0.02	100	0.01	
12:46:00	FL140	3	0.07	0					962	0		0		0			
12:49:00	FL140	3	0.06	0					962	0		0		0			
12:50:00	FL150	10	0.05	2	275			5,11,12,8	962	0		0		0.001	100		PROFILE 14
12:51:08	FL160	3	0.06	5	375			5,11,8	962	0		0		0.002	250		RUN 13
12:55:00	FL160	3	0.07	18	325			8,11	963	0		0		0.001	100	1.0	
12:57:00	FL160	4	0.11	11	450			8,11	963	0		1	10	0.005	1000		
13:01:00	FL160	1	0.11	2	650			8,11	965	0		1	8	0.001	500		
13:03:00	FL160	1	0.11	1	600			8,11	966	0		1	5	0.003	550	1.1	
13:06:00	FL160	6	0.25	10	750			8,11,12	967	0		1	8	0.001	450	0.85	
13:06:47	FL170	2	0.10	6	525			8,11	968	0		1	8	0.003	500	0.62	
13:07:45	FL180	4	0.55	24	550			8,11	968	0		6	7	0.004	450	0.62	
13:12:00	FL180	3	0.08	2	200			11	969	0		0		0			
13:14:31	FL190	3	0.21	35	550			11,4	970	NOISE		1	10	0.006	200	0.43	
13:15:44	FL200	2	0.06	12	400			11, 8, 4	970	NOISE		1	4	0.002	100	0.44	RUN 15.1
13:18:00	FL200	2	0.06	1	250			11, 8	970	0		0		0			
13:21:00	FL200	1	0.08	0					970	0		0		0			
13:23:00	FL200	7	0.06	0					970	0		0		0			DAT OBSERVED
13:25:00	FL200	12	0.07	3	200			11,8	970	0		0		0			
13:28:49	FL190	3	0.05	0					970	0		0		0			PROFILE 17
13:31:00	FL190	4	0.09	6	300			8	972	0		0		0.001	200	1.49	
13:33:00	FL190	3	0.09	1	300			8	972	0		0		0			
13:35:38	FL180	3	0.07	0					972	0		0		0			
13:36:46	FL170	15	0.06	2	200			8,11	972	0		0		0			RUN 17.1
13:38:00	FL170	2	0.06	0					972	0		0		0			

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B426 **T/O:** 08:42:05
Date of flight: 28/01/09 **Land:** 14:07:37

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	<p>1</p> <p>8</p>	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = 083500 End = 141500</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 8984</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	<p>Y</p>	<p>X = Y = (X+1) = tas_2d</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B426
Date of Flight: 28/01/09

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 0.92
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = _tas_2d Y = X+1 = tas_2d_pcasp
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Y Use flight_plot to check.

Flight:

B426

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nezvorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B426

Date: 28/1/09

Issues

Instruments

Horace	OK
Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	OK
Nevzerov	OK
Buck -	OK
FWVS	Not working
Turbulence	OK
2ds	OK – minor icing
CAPS	OK
CDP	OK
Total Water	OK

Aircraft

SatcomC	ops normal
MPDS	Worked fine

ISDN Emails	Not used
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

Chilbolton (51.15N 1.44W)

Chilbolton Radar Images – B426 28 Jan 2009

Latest 4 hours

Today

B426 rad2.bmp

Today

B426 RADCHOB_RT_Merged.bmp

B426 chb_ref-1.bmp

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 28 Jan 2009 10:57:50 RHI 8003/248 Azim 255.0°

B426 radrh1_4_B426.bmp

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 28 Jan 2009 11:30:07 RHI 8003/258 Azim 255.0°

B426 radrh1_5_B426.bmp

Latest 4 hours

UFAM/Chilbolton 35-GHz Cloud Radar (Copernicus)

Today

B426 radrh1_6_B426.bmp

B426 radrh1_7_B426.bmp

B426 radrh1_8_B426.bmp

B426 radrh1_9_B426.bmp

3-GHz radar

Wednesday 28 Jan 2009 12:54:05 RHI 8003/284 Azim 255.0°

B426 radrh1_10_B426.bmp